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AXBOROT OQIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA WEB ILOVALARNI YARATISH VA QO'LLASH USULLARI.

Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti,

1-bosqich magistrant.

maqsudu32@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu Maqola Axborot Oqimini Shakllantirishda Web Ilovalarni Yaratish Va Qo'llash Usullari Haqida Bo'lib Mavzu Yuzasidan Tadqiqotchi Olimlarning Fikr Va Mulohazalari Chuqur O'rganib Chiqildi.

Kalit So'zlar: Iqtisodiyot, Tijorat Banklari, Axborot Oqimi, Moliya Tizimi, Innovatsion Texnologiyalar, Web Ilovalar, It Texnologiyalar, Dasturlash, Ilovalar Yaratish, Web-Developer.

Аннотация: В Данной Статье Речь Пойдет О Методах Создания И Использования Веб-Приложений При Формировании Поточка Информации.

Ключевые Слова: Экономика, Коммерческие Банки, Информационный Поток, Финансовая Система, Инновационные Технологии, Веб-Приложения, It-Технологии, Программирование, Разработка Приложений, Веб-Разработчик.

Abstract: This Article Is About The Methods Of Creating And Using Web Applications In The Formation Of The Flow Of Information.

Keywords: Economics, Commercial Banks, Information Flow, Financial System, Innovative Technologies, Web Applications, It Technologies, Programming, Application Development, Web-Developer

Bugungi Kunda Jamiyatimiz Hayotining Deyarli Barcha Jabhasida Globallashuv Jarayonlari Ya'ni Har Bir Sohada Juda Katta Rivojlanishlar Va Yangiliklar Yaratilmoqda Va Dunyo Yuzini Ko'rmoqda. Fan-Ta'lim, Iqtisodiyot, Madaniyat, Xalqaro Munosabatlar Yoinki Barcha Sohalarida Yangi Innovatsion Texnologiyalar Orqali Yaratilgan Yoki Innovatsion G'oyalarga Asoslangan Loyihalar Asosida Barpo Etilgan Yangiliklarni Ko'rishimiz Mumkin. Ayniqsa, Innovatsion Texnologiyalar Asosida It Texnologiyalari Ko'magida Amalga Oshirilayotgan Islohotlarning Ko'lami Ham Ortib Bormoqda. Xuddi Shuningdek Ushbu Jarayon Barcha Sohalar Qatori Iqtisodiyotda Ham Keng Qo'llanilmoqda. Ushbu Jarayonlarning Tub Markazida Xxi Asr Uchun Eng Katta Kuch Hisoblangan - "Axborot" Tushunchasi Yotadi. Haqiqatdan Ham, Bugungi Kunda Kim Eng Aniq, Eng Tezkor, Eng Ishoonchli Va Eng Haqqoniy Axborotga Ega Bo'lsa Va Ularni Atrofidagi Insonlari Bemalol Bo'lishishi Mumkin. Fikrimizning Yorqin Isboti Sifatida Birgina Mamlakatimiz Iqtisodiyot Tizimiga Bir Nazara Tashlasak. Binobarin, Oddiygina Tijorat Banklarida Ham

Axborot Oqimini Shakllantirishda, Sifatli Axborot Almashinuvini Yo'lga Qo'yishda Va Sifatli Tarzda Ushbu Jarayonni Davom Ettirishda Ushbu Texnologiyalarning O'rni Juda Beqiyosdir. Umuman Olganda, Insoniyat Hayotining Har Bir Lahzasi Allaqachon Turli Xil Mana Shunday Gadgetlarga Tayangan Holda Yashashga Moslashib Ulgurgan. Bu Degani, Odamlar Turmushida Har Bir Faoliyat Turi Bo'ladimi, Yoki Xizmat Ko'rsatishi Sohasi Bo'ladimi Barcha- Barchasini Ushbu Innovatsion, Yangi Va Eng Muhimi Samarali Katta Tezlikda Ishlashga Mo'ljallangan Qurilmalar Qamrab Olgan .

Adabiyotlar Tahlili Va Metodlar

Shu Nuqtai Nazardan Olib Qaraydigan Bo'lsak, Bu Qurilmalar It, Texnologiyalarni Yaratishda, Akashf Etishda Va Amalda Qo'llashda Ushbu Sohada Yetuk Mutaxassis Kadrlar Yetishib Chiqmoqda : Dasturchilar, It Sohasida Ishlovchi Mutaxassislar, Bloggerlar, Smm Mutaxassislari, Web-Dizaynerlar, Web-Developerlar, Grafik Dizaynerlar Va Hokazolar. Ushbu Axborot Olami Kasblari Orasida Har Qanday Soha Uchun Web Dasturlarni Va Web Ilovalarni Yaratuvchi Web Developerlarning Ham O'z O'rni Bor. Ya'nikim, Web Developerlar - Aynan, Barcha Sohalar Uchun Zarur Bo'lgan Qulay, Tezkor, Turli Xil Afzalliklarga Ega Xilma-Xil Mobil Ilovalarni Yaratuvchi Internet Mutaxassislaridir. Ushbu Kasbning Mohiyati Shundan Iboratki, Web Developerlar Yangidan-Yangi Ilovalar Loyihalarini Yaratadi Va Ularni Takomillashfirib Boradi.

Web Developer Bilishi Kerak Bo'lgan Eng Muhim Atamalar Mavjud Bo'lib Ular Quyidagilardir:

1. Algoritm Ma'lum Vazifalarni Bajarish Uchun Qadamlar To'plami. Kompyuter Dasturlashida Algoritmalar Muammoni Hal Qilishning Muhim Qismi Hisoblanadi. Algoritmni Yaratishda, Developerlar Muammoni Hal Qilish Uchun Barcha Zarur Qadamlarni Va Har Bir Bosqich Nimani O'z Ichiga Olganligini Hujjatlashtiradi.

Api - Application Programming Interface. Api Ikkita Turli Xil Dasturlarni Developerlarga Veb-Sayt Kodining Ba'zi Qismlarini Taqdim Etish Orqali Bir-Biri Bilan Aloqa Qilish Imkon Beradi. Developerlar Ushbu Kodni, Ya'ni Apini Ushbu Veb-Saytga Ulanadigan Vositalar Va Vidjetlarni Yaratish Uchun Ishlatishlari Mumkin. Misol Uchun, Saytingizda Google Orqali Ro'yxatdan O'tish Imkonini Berish Uchun Google Api - Dan Foydalansiz.

3. App Yoki Application: Siz, Shubhasiz, Application (Ilova) Bilan Tanishsiz Va Har Kuni Ulardan Bir Nechtasini Ishlatasiz. Application, Asosan, Foydalanuvchiga Turli Xil Vazifalarni Bajarishga Imkon Beradigan Dastur.

Misol Uchun Telegram Bu Ham Application. Developer Sifatida, Desktop App, Mobile App Va Web Applar Orasidagi Farqni Tushinishingiz Kerak.

4. Frontend: Veb-Saytning Tashqi Ko'rinishi - Bu Foydalanuvchi Ko'radigan Va Ishlatadigan Qism. Frontend Tillari Html, Css Va Javascriptni O'z Ichiga Oladi, Ularning Barchasi Veb-Saytning Tashqi Ko'rinishini Boshqaradi.

5. Backend: Veb-Saytning Server Tomonida Ishlaydigan Kod, Bu Backend Kodi Deyiladi. Backend Ma'lumotlar Ba'zasiga Ma'lumotlarni Joylash, Tahrirlash Va O'chirish Va Saytning Ort Tomonida Bajariladigan Barcha Logikani O'z Ichiga Oladi.

Xohlaymizmi, Yo'qmi Saytlarga Nisbatan Mobil Ilova (App)Lardan Ko'proq Foydalanilayapti Va Ular Web Saytlarga Nisbatan Ko'proq Mashhurlikka Erishmoqda. Shuning Uchun Saytlar Tayyorlashga Nisbatan Mobil Ilovalar Tayyorlash Narxi Ancha Yuqori.

Muhokama Va Natijalar

Mobil Ilovalar Texnologiyasiga Ko'ra Ikkita Gigant: Android Va Ios Asosida Tayyorlanadi. Ularning Har Biriga Dastur Tayyorlashingiz Uchun Ma'lum Yo'nalishdagi Ko'nikma Va Bilimlarga Ega Bo'lish Kerak. Faqat Android Yoki Faqat Ios Uchun Ilova Yozuvchi Dasturchilarga Bo'lgan Talab Juda Yuqori Ekanligini Ko'rgan Kishi Ham Android, Ham Ios Uchun Dastur Yoza Oladigan Dasturchining Talabgorligini Tasavvur Qilib Olishi Mumkin.

Faqatgina Html/Css Va Javascript Ishlatgan Holda To'liq Dinamik Web Sayt Tayyorlash Ancha Qiyin Ish. Ammo Html/Css Va Js Kabi Nisbatan Oson O'rganiladigan Ko'nikmalardan Foydalangan Holda Mobil Ilovalar Tayyorlay Olish Web Saytlar Tayyorlashga Nisbatan Olib Qaralganda Imkonsizdek Tuyuladi. Qolaversa, Mobil Qurilmalar Uchun Ilova Tayyorlash Web Saytlar Tayyorlashga Nisbatan Ancha Qimmat VaQadrli Ko'nikma Hisoblanadi.

Veb-Ilovalar Javascript , Css Va Html5 Dasturlash Tillari Asosida Yaratiladi. . Mobil Ilovalardan Farqli O'laroq, Veb-Ilovalarni Yaratish Uchun Standart Dasturiy Ta'minot Ishlab Chiqish To'plami Mavjud Emas. Biroq, Ishlab Chiquvchilar Shablonlarga Kirish Huquqiga Ega. Mobil Ilovalar Bilan Taqqoslaganda, Veb-Ilovalar Odatda Tezroq Va Osonroq Tuziladi, Ammo Xususiyatlari Jihatidan Ular Ancha Sodda. Agar Siz Html, Css Va Javascript-Ni O'rganishni Xohlasangiz, Ushbu Bepul Faqatgina Html/Css Va Javascript Ishlatgan Holda To'liq Dinamik Web Sayt Tayyorlash Ancha Qiyin Ish. Ammo Html/Css Va Js Kabi Nisbatan Oson O'rganiladigan Ko'nikmalardan Foydalangan Holda Mobil Ilovalar Tayyorlay Olish Web Saytlar Tayyorlashga

Nisbatan Olib Qaralganda Imkonsizdek Tuyuladi. Qolaversa, Mobil Qurilmalar Uchun Ilova Tayyorlash Web Saytlar Tayyorlashga Nisbatan Ancha Qimmat Va Qadrli Ko'nikma Hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

Veb-Ilovalarni Ishga Tushirish Uchun Faol Internet Aloqasi Zarur, Mobil Ilovalar Esa Oflayn Rejimda Ishlashi Mumkin. Mobil Ilovalar Tezroq Va Samaraliroq Bo'lishining Afzalliklariga Ega, Ammo Ular Foydalanuvchidan Doimiy Ravishda Yangilanishlarni Yuklab Olishni Talab Qiladi. Veb-Ilovalar O'zlarini O'zlari Yangilaydi.

Oddiy Veb-Ilovalardan (Va Mahalliy Mobil Ilovalarga O'xshash) Farqli O'laroq, Ilg'or Veb-Ilovalar Oflayn Rejimda Ishlaydi Va Juda Tez Yuklanadi. Bu, Avvalambor, Zamonaviy Brauzerning Takomillashuviga Bog'liq: Application Cache Xususiyati Tufayli Veb-Saytlar Endi Katta Hajmdagi Ma'lumotlarni Oflayn Rejimda Saqlashi Mumkin. Shuning Uchun Ilg'or Veb-Ilovalarni Internetga Ulanmasdan Ishlatish Mumkin, Bu Ularga Odatiy Mahalliy Mobil Ilovalar Funktsiyalarini Beradi, Masalan, Push Xabarnomalari, Mahalliy Video Va Audio Yozib Olish Va Mahalliy Videoni Ijro Etish.

Xuddi Standart Veb-Ilovalar Singari, Progressiv Veb-Ilovalar Yuklab Olish Yoki O'rnatishni Talab Qilmaydi. Ko'p Jihatdan Ular Ikkala Dunyoning Eng Yaxshisini Taklif Qilgandek. Ushbu Atamani Ixtiro Qilgan Aleks Russell Ularni Quyidagicha Ta'riflaganidek: Pwalar "Sezgir, Ulanishga Bog'liq Bo'lmagan, Dasturga O'xshash, Yangi, Xavfsiz, Kashf Etiladigan, Qayta Bog'lanadigan, O'rnatiladigan Va Bog'lanadigan Veb-Tajribalardir".

Xulosa Qilib Aytganda, Mana Shu Ketma-Ketlik Va Tartibga Asoslangan Holda Iqtisodiyotga Ham, Tijorat Banklarida Ham Axborot Oqimini Ishonchli Va Sifatli Tarzda Shakllantirishda Dasturlashning O'zingizga Ma'qul Bo'lgan Dasturlash Tili Orqali Bemalol Web Ilova Yaratishingiz, Unga Yangi Funktsiyalar Qo'shishingiz Va Albatta Uni Takomillashtirib Borishingiz Mumkin Bo'ladi.

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FUNKSIYANING ANIQLANISH SOHASI, GRAFIGI, LIMITI VA UZLUKSIZLIGI ,
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